

ROADMAP

Rethinking of antimicrobial decision-systems in the management of animal production

Research and Innovation action: H2020 – 817626
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D7.2 Website online and communication package

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DELIVERABLE D7.2

Workpackage N°7

Due date: M6

Dissemination level: Public

About the ROADMAP research project

The overall aim of ROADMAP is to **foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials (AMs) in animal production in different contexts to manage antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Prudent antimicrobial use (AMU) will be achieved by enhancing antimicrobial decision-systems along the food and drug supply chains.** ROADMAP will focus on supporting animal health and welfare through prevention and health promotion actions.

AMR is recognized as a significant threat to global public health and food security. Overuse and improper use of AMs in many parts of the world contribute to the emergence and spread of AMR. Although human and animal health require AMs, it has been estimated that two thirds of the future AMU growth worldwide will be in animal production. Improving the management of AMU in farm animals is therefore a critical component of dealing with AMR and optimizing production in the livestock sector. Nevertheless, the variety of contexts of AMU in the livestock sector is a major challenge to managing AMR. **There is no “one-size-fits-all” solution to improve AMU and strategies must be contextually developed** (for instance, strategies used in the Danish pig industry are difficult to adapt and adopt in the French free-range poultry farming). Successful solutions must be combined and tailored to the production systems and the social and economic context in which they operate.

ROADMAP will meet three general objectives, in line with the EU AMR Action plan: i) **Rethink AM decision-systems and animal health management**; ii) **Develop options for encouraging prudent AMU in animal production**; iii) **Engage all actors in the food and drug supply chains in fostering a more prudent use of AMs.**

Project consortium

Partner N°	Participant organisation name (acronym)	Country
1	Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique (INRA) **	France
2	Association de coordination technique agricole (ACTA) ***	France
3	Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement (CIRAD) **	France
4	University of Liverpool (ULIV) *	United Kingdom
5	Cardiff University (CU) *	United Kingdom
6	James Hutton Institute (HUT) **	United Kingdom
7	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna (UNIBO) *	Italy
8	Aarhus Universitet (AU) *	Denmark
9	Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw en Visserijonderzoek (EV-ILVO) **	Belgium
10	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL) **	Switzerland
11	Stichting Wageningen Research (WR) *	Netherlands
12	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) *	Sweden
13	Southern Agriculture and Horticulture Organization (ZLTO) ***	Netherlands
14	European Forum of Farm Animal Breeders (EFFAB) ****	Netherlands
15	Fundacion Empresa Universidad Gallega (FEUGA) ****	Spain
16	Dierengezondheidszorg Vlaanderen (DGZ) ***	Belgium
17	INRA Transfert (IT) ****	France

* Universities/veterinary schools

** Research institutes specialized in both fundamental and applied agricultural and veterinary sciences

*** Public and private advisory services Organisations

**** Knowledge transfer and Innovation Organisations

Table of Contents

List of acronyms and abbreviations	6
1 Summary.....	7
2 Introduction	7
3 Project identity.....	7
3.1 Project Logo	8
3.2 Font	8
3.3 Colours	9
3.4 Language	9
3.5 EU logo and acknowledgement	9
3.6 Project Message.....	10
3.6.1 Tagline.....	10
3.6.2 Communication message.....	10
3.7 Project templates.....	10
3.7.1 Email signature	11
3.7.2 Poster template	11
3.7.3 PowerPoint presentation template	12
3.7.4 Letter template	12
3.7.5 Agenda template	12
3.7.6 Meeting Minutes template.....	13
4 ROADMAP Website	14
4.1 Summary	14
4.2 Objectives	14
4.3 Methods.....	14
4.4 Results and Implications	15
4.5 Cookies.....	15
4.6 Site Map and pages.....	15
4.6.1 Homepage.....	16
4.6.2 Project.....	16
4.6.3 Results.....	18
4.6.4 News & Events	18
4.6.5 Stakeholders	18
4.6.6 Media	19

4.6.7	External Networks.....	20
4.6.8	Contact.....	20
5	Social media accounts	21
6	Conclusion.....	22
7	Annex	23

List of acronyms and abbreviations

AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
AMU	Antimicrobial Use
EFFAB	European Forum of Farm Animal Breeders
EIP-AGRI	The Agricultural European Innovation Partnership
EU	European Union
FABRE TP	Farm Animal Breeding and Reproduction Technology Platform
ODP	Outreach and Dissemination Plan
WP	Work Package

1 Summary

D7.2 consists of the launch of the ROADMAP website and the preparation of a communication package to be used all along the project period. Project website is the main portal for the external actors and stakeholders to get first-hand information on project, its structure, partners, objectives, expected impacts and results. It aims to provide full summary of the project supported by differentiated content for different stakeholder group. It will also host the document sharing platform for the stakeholders, links to different social media channels of ROADMAP and the ROADMAP stakeholder platform on Facebook where it is possible to actively involve in discussions without any language barriers. Website will also provide a media kit for different actors including brochures, fact sheets, press releases, policy briefs, practice abstracts, newsletters, audio visual materials, informative presentations, and the ROADMAP movie.

The communication package on the other hand will provide the ROADMAP partners with unified designs for different communication materials such as posters, powerpoint slides, letters, agenda and minutes. It is very important that both EU flag, ROADMAP logo and the EU acknowledgement is visible through out all the published documents in the project.

2 Introduction

Within the WP7, communication activities will be carried out throughout the project targeting different level stakeholder groups under ROADMAP Outreach and Dissemination Plan (ODP). The ODP will be continuously updated including the input from stakeholders. ODP will highlight the use of different communication and dissemination tools as well as a specific chapter on exploitation of project outcomes.

Communication activities include the implementation of offline and online, conventional and innovative communication methods such as the creation of a project identity and communication material templates (such as poster, powerpoint presentation, agenda, minutes of the meeting, etc.) in form of “ROADMAP book of style”, project website which will be maintained for 2 more years after the project, social media management, press releases, digital newsletters, promotional materials such as project brochures, banners, infographic, popular articles for online magazines, audio-visual materials such as interviews, presentations with commentaries and a ROADMAP animated video to raise awareness to AMR and communicate the integrative strategies to public and policy makers. ROADMAP video will be communicated through ROADMAP TV at YouTube channel and will be promoted through social media channels (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn) of the project as well as EFFAB and FABRE-TP networks. Popular agricultural media channels and online magazines will also be used to reach to a wider audience.

3 Project identity

To make sure that the ROADMAP project appears coherent and consistent in all communication materials related to the project, a project identity and accompanying guidelines are produced. All participants are encouraged to follow the guidelines, for presentations, brochures, newsletters, publications etc. All official material for the European Commission and general public must be in accordance with the guidelines.

3.1 Project Logo

The ROADMAP logo has been designed for branding the project in all communication forms. Humans are in the center of the logo because they are the main elements of ROADMAP project (which is about understanding behaviors and strategies of stakeholders) and also the main population threatened by the risks of antimicrobial resistance. The ROADMAP logo shows people on the crossroads that lead to different directions since we consider there is a diversity of pathways to foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials. Animal heads are linked to circular paths referring to “ONE HEALTH” approach, highlighting the connection between human, health, animal health and the environment.

The logo is available in different versions:

- Logo with acronym title
- Logos with project titles
- File formats PNG, EPS and JPEG
 - o Normally use PNG or JPEG
 - o Use EPS for graphic purposes
- Colored with white or without background and white without background
 - o Use logo on white background.
 - o Logo on top of photos should be printed on a white background

The logo files will be placed on the collaborative platform of the project. The text font used for the ROADMAP logo is **Arboria Medium** whereas the Payoff is **Futura Medium**.

Figure 1 ROADMAP Logo with acronym only and including the title

3.2 Font

Font in logo is Arboria Medium whereas the Payoff is Futura Medium, but this is not standard in Microsoft. Therefore, Calibri will be used as the primary font of ROADMAP, as it is standard in Microsoft. Text font for PowerPoints, documents, posters etc. is Calibri. The standard font size is 11 and the main text colour is black. For hierarchical headlines, the style should be Calibri. Example of heading 1, 2 and 3:

Heading 1

Heading 2

Heading 3

Heading 4

3.3 Colours

The colours used in the ROADMAP logo are given below with RGB codes.

Logo colors	Hex code	Red	Green	Blue	Color
Red	#D33215	211	50	21	
Green	#6CA727	108	167	39	
Gray	#5A5552	90	85	82	

The colours used in the ROADMAP logo are given below with CMYK codes.

Logo colors	Cyan	Magenta	Yellow	Key	Color
Red	8	90	100	4	
Green	60	0	100	13	
Gray	30	30	30	67	

3.4 Language

The language used between all ROADMAP partners, stakeholders and in the reports to the EU is **British English**. In addition, all partners are free and encouraged to promote the ROADMAP activities in the language of their own country.

3.5 EU logo and acknowledgement

Along with the ROADMAP logo, the EU flag should be visible on all communications from the ROADMAP project.

Link to graphic design of EU-projects:

http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information/logos/index_en.cfm

Please note that any **dissemination** and any **communication** activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must include this information:

This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817626.

3.6 Project Message

3.6.1 Tagline

The tagline describes the essence of the project in a short and understandable way, linking to why this is important for the target audiences. This is used on communication materials (website, brochure, presentations, etc.).

Currently used and proposed taglines:

“Rethinking of Antimicrobial Decision-systems in the Management of Animal Production”

“Understanding sociotechnical and socioeconomic drivers of AMU”

“Tailoring contextualized strategies to foster prudent AMU in diverse production systems in Europe and worldwide”

“Developing innovative socioeconomic and technical instruments to foster prudent AMU adapted to various production systems”

“Fighting against antimicrobial resistance by allowing cross-learning from diverse successful experiences”

“Encouraging a harmonization of AMU reduction trends across Europe”

“Favoring a global decrease of AMU in animal production”

3.6.2 Communication message

The communication message consists of one general message which should be further specified per target group. It will create the ‘external identity’ of the project. The message must be simple, clear and positive. This main communication message is:

ROADMAP aims to foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials (AMs) in animal production in different contexts to manage antimicrobial resistance (AMR). ROADMAP will analyze sociotechnical and socioeconomic drivers of AMU and develop innovative strategies to promote prudent AMU, based on social sciences, interdisciplinary and participatory approaches.

3.7 Project templates

There are several communication templates with the ROADMAP profile which will be used in the management of ROADMAP and in all official collaborations and reporting. The partners and also stakeholders in ROADMAP are encouraged to use them. In the presentations and posters involved in the ROADMAP project, always use the ROADMAP logo, accompanied by the EU flag.

The templates of ROADMAP communication templates below are available and could be found on the internal collaborative platform. They are also given in the Annex part.

3.7.1 Email signature

The email signature for Outlook includes the ROADMAP logo with a link to the ROADMAP website, followed by the icons of ROADMAP's social media accounts. ROADMAP partners can write their names, positions in the organisation, name of the organisation, phone number, email address and the logo of their organisation in the email signature of ROADMAP.

<http://www.roadmap-h2020.eu>

Name

Position

Name of the Organisation

Phone number

Email

Logo of the Organization

Figure 2 ROADMAP email signature

3.7.2 Poster template

The poster template of ROADMAP includes the ROADMAP logo on the top left corner and the logo of the partner organisation on the top right corner of the poster. EU acknowledgement is the key for all documents produced under ROADMAP project. **(Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.)**

Figure 3 ROADMAP poster template

3.7.3 PowerPoint presentation template

The powerpoint template of ROADMAP includes the ROADMAP logo on the top right corner. Using of the logo of the partner organisation on the top leftt corner of the title slide is optional. EU acknowledgement is the key for all documents produced under ROADMAP project. **(Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.)**

Figure 4 ROADMAP presentation template

3.7.4 Letter template

The letter template of ROADMAP includes the ROADMAP logo on the top left corner. EU acknowledgement is the key for all documents produced under ROADMAP project. **(Erreur ! Source du**

renvoi introuvable.)

Figure 5 ROADMAP letter template

3.7.5 Agenda template

The agenda template of ROADMAP includes the ROADMAP logo on the top left corner. EU acknowledgement is the key for all documents produced under ROADMAP project. **(Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.)**

Figure 6 ROADMAP agenda template

3.7.6 Meeting Minutes template

The meeting minutes template of ROADMAP includes the ROADMAP logo on the top left corner. EU acknowledgement is the key for all documents produced under ROADMAP project. **(Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.)**

Figure 7 ROADMAP minutes of the meeting template

4 ROADMAP Website

ROADMAP communication strategy targets stakeholders and end-users such as animal health professionals (veterinarians, technicians), farmers, breeding and feeding industries, pharmaceutical companies, retailers, processors, public authorities. Chosen communication tools and materials aim to target different audiences with different methods and channels selected to be used under ROADMAP project.

4.1 Summary

The ROADMAP website is an important communication tool that requires continuous updating during the course of the project. It is the major communication and dissemination tool for the project. It presents the project objectives, work plan, highlights major results, presents the project partners and stakeholders, including electronic versions of training courses, links to other EU or international projects and stakeholder associations and contact details of relevant partners within the project. It also includes press releases, news and events, and a link to the YouTube channel where video materials, e-trainings and webinars are posted. The goal is to keep the website informative, up-to-date, inspiring and inclusive, so that it invites visitors to further engage with the project. Project website will be maintained for 2 more years after the project.

The project website link is <https://www.roadmap-h2020.eu>. The website covers the following content:

- Press releases and latest news
- Calendar and information on project events
- Project brochures
- Digital newsletters
- Audio-visual materials
- Stakeholder Platform
- E-trainings and webinars
- Scientific publications, presentations form conferences and proceedings of workshops
- Links to related national and international EU projects

EFFAB is responsible for the design and content of the ROADMAP website. All partners are requested to make a link to the ROADMAP website on their own website.

4.2 Objectives

To communicate up-to-date information on the project, the partners involved, the background of the project and on the project activities, the outcomes and the meaning of the outcomes.

4.3 Methods

A website is designed using the web-hosting service 'Weebly', with an online website creator. The ROADMAP website will be further developed during the project lifetime by gathering and publishing information from its work packages.

4.4 Results and Implications

A ROADMAP dedicated website that informs the project members, stakeholders and the wider public about project activities. It will serve as an important first contact point for the targeted audience.

4.5 Cookies

The website follows the Commission's guidelines on privacy and data protection and inform users that cookies are not being used to gather information unnecessarily. The ePrivacy Directive – more specifically Article 5(3) – requires prior informed consent for storage or for access to information stored on a user's terminal equipment.

4.6 Site Map and pages

The site map for the website is shown below. In addition to provide basic information about the project it will provide information about the involved countries, including the stakeholder activities. Further it will provide up-to-date information about project progress and events, communication and dissemination materials.

Figure 8 Website map of ROADMAP

4.6.1 Homepage

Homepage includes a brief overview of the whole project website. It shows the most recent updates of the project, ROADMAP’s social media account buttons and ROADMAP Twitter feed. It also includes subscription button to ROADMAP newsletter.

4.6.2 Project

Project page includes a brief overview of the project and it summarizes the ROADMAP objectives. It has 3 subpages; Impact, Structure and Partners.

- Impact page summarizes the expected impacts of the project on various target audiences.
- Structure page gives information on the project work plan and its work packages.

- Partners page gives the map view of all partner’s organisations, the list of partners in the consortium with links to their websites, short information about the partner organisation, main tasks of the organisation within the project and the key personnel working in the project.

The overall aim of ROADMAP is to foster transitions towards prudent AMU in animal production in a large variety of contexts to manage AME. This AMU reduction will be achieved through an improvement of antimicrobial decision-systems all along the food and drug supply chain. The originality of ROADMAP lies on the fact that for the first time a project will apply "Food supply chain" and "Transition pathways" conceptual approaches to AMU topics. So far, research has focused on technical solutions and behavioural change, but not on a broader understanding of the systemic dynamics and therefore required changes. ROADMAP's new theoretical and methodological framework allows it and will bring new knowledge and solutions to the crucial issue of reducing AMU in animal production.

Through the interdisciplinary and multi-actor perspective which will be developed within the living labs methodology, ROADMAP will tackle the most important challenge of the fight against AMR, i.e. finding solutions that are adapted to local contexts. It will draw lessons from countries and production systems that have already decreased AMU and rely on successful experiences to build transition scenarios and pathways that can mobilise all actors involved in animal health management (from the farmers and the veterinarians to upstream and downstream industries and public authorities). Moreover, by carrying out fieldwork from different regions of Europe and LMIC countries, ROADMAP will contribute to homogenise and harmonise trends and dynamics towards prudent use of AMs in farmed animals.

Finally, ROADMAP will have an impact on a large range of actors involved in rethinking of animal production management. By combining economics, social, animal and veterinary sciences, ROADMAP will not only provide efficient technical solutions for fostering prudent AMU, but also come up with socioeconomic tools and incentives that will ensure their acceptability and thus implementation. Transition pathways engaging all the food and drug supply chain will indeed make it possible to favour a global reduction of AMU, driven by a mix of several strategies adapted to the specific issues faced by different production systems.

Global impact

"Contribute to the fight against AMR arising from farmed animal production" and to a global reduction of AMU and its impact on environment, animal health and public health (One Health approach)".

By identifying the main AMU drivers and studying current practices in different contexts, ROADMAP will contribute to a global reduction of AMU through a rethinking of antimicrobial decision-systems in the management of animal production. In particular, ROADMAP will contribute to:

- The protection of animal health and welfare through improved animal health prevention and control;
- The protection of human health through the preservation of the antibiotic arsenal, a better control of the spread of resistant bacteria and improvement of food safety and food security;
- The protection of the environment by a better control of the spread of resistant bacteria (through farm waste in particular).

IMPACT FOR FARMERS	+
IMPACT FOR VETERINARIANS	+
IMPACT FOR PUBLIC AUTHORITIES	+
IMPACT FOR ACADEMIA	+
IMPACT FOR ALL ACTORS	+

4.6.3 Results

Results page consists of 3 pages giving access to deliverables, Living Labs and scientific publications. This page will be developed and improved as the project results are produced.

4.6.4 News & Events

These pages are intended to inform about the project progress and events.

4.6.5 Stakeholders

Stakeholder page informs about the stakeholder inclusion and engagement strategy of ROADMAP. It has 2 subpages; invitation to the Stakeholder Community and Stakeholder Repository. The stakeholder's repository will be an online space within a specific section of the ROADMAP website where stakeholders can contribute, interact and stay tuned with the news, events and work developed through the project. It will be developed and managed by FEUGA, and it will include links to Facebook Stakeholders' Community developed and managed by EFFAB to reach and foster interactions with stakeholders. All the specifications and operational information is provided in deliverable D7.1 Stakeholders Engagement.

HOME
PROJECT
RESULTS
NEWS & EVENTS
STAKEHOLDERS
CONTACT

NEWS & EVENTS

ISESSAH-2020 CONFERENCE

14 – 16 MAY 2020, COPENHAGEN

14/11/2019

The International Society for Economics and Social Sciences of Animal Health (ISESSAH) was formed at the final NEAT-meeting with the intention to carry on the work of NEAT and to include the field of social science in veterinary related issues. ISESSAH aims to improve animal health and welfare policies, programme and projects through more nuanced use of concepts and tools available in economics and social science disciplines. In the process it will provide opportunities for animal health professionals globally to achieve wider societal benefits from animals in society.

The ISESSAH 2020 conference will be take place on **14 – 16th May 2020** in **Copenhagen**. The main topic will be **"Economics and social science applied to animal health surveillance"**. The deadline for the submission of abstracts is **29th of November 2019**. For more information, please visit the website.

ROADMAP PARTICIPATED IN FITTER LIVESTOCK FARMING WORKSHOP

07/11/2019

ROADMAP participated in the FitterLivestockFarming Workshop about "What RM can deliver to support climate mitigation and adaptation in livestockfarming on 5 November 2019 in Brussels, Belgium. The workshop was jointly organized by Animal Task Force (ATF) and Common Disinfection Booster (CDB) cluster projects. Maria-Helene Finard talked about the aim of the ROADMAP project and mentioned that linking health and management data with the environmental data is crucial. This workshop brought together animal scientists with livestock professionals and advisors, as well as researchers, non-profit & societal organisations and industry representatives. By joining this workshop, ROADMAP had a chance to meet the stakeholders in the early project's lifetime.

FRUITFULL KICK-OFF MEETING ROADMAP

16/06/2019

ROADMAP project's fruitful kick-off meeting took place in Paris on 18 June 2019:

Follow ROADMAP

Tweets by @ROADMAP_H2020

ROADMAP (@ROADMAP_H2020) Retweeted

#ISESSAH2020 Conference will take place on 14-16 May 2020 in Copenhagen. The main topic is "Economics and social science applied to animal health surveillance". Deadline for abstracts: 29 November? For more information: roadmap-h2020.eu/news-events/... #AMR #AMR

48m

ROADMAP Retweeted

Nicolas Fortané (@fortane) Glad to announce that @ClaireFischer, Maria Escobar and I are co-editing a special issue in @FrontVetScience on interdisciplinary and social science approaches to AMU in livestock. Please consult, apply and contact us if you have any questions! frontiers.org/newsarchive/...

Oct 29, 2019

ROADMAP Retweeted

Isamara Gilez-Verned (@GilezVerned) Successful work on #AMR

Embed View on Tweet

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🐦
in
👤

HOME
PROJECT
RESULTS
NEWS & EVENTS
STAKEHOLDERS
CONTACT

ROADMAP STAKEHOLDERS COMMUNITY

Do you want to contribute, interact, and stay tuned to foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials (AMs) in animal production in different contexts to manage antimicrobial resistance (AMR)?

JOIN OUR STAKEHOLDER PLATFORM!

ROADMAP is a multi-actor approach project where stakeholders have been involved since the project set-up and will continue to be involved throughout the project. Since stakeholders will also be the end-users of the project results, they will be permanently involved and play an important role in achieving ROADMAP's main goal. Project partners and the stakeholders' platform members represented by the Stakeholders Advisory Board work together during the project to guide the participatory research and ensure that ROADMAP outputs are applicable. The Stakeholder Platform will be consulted regularly to ensure that results of ROADMAP project match the needs and expectations of stakeholders.

CONTRIBUTE

Share your insights, knowledge and opinion with the ROADMAP consortium by sending us an e-mail

GET IN TOUCH

INTERACT

Interact with other stakeholders and project partners to guide the ROADMAP project

CONNECT TO OUR STAKEHOLDER PLATFORM

STAY TUNED

Subscribe to our newsletter and receive updates on our progress and achievements

SUBSCRIBE TO NEWSLETTER

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4.6.6 Media

This page aims to provide the different targeted audiences with the right communication and dissemination material. It will cover all the publications whether technical, scientific or popular. Different media tools will be used during ROADMAP project including informative brochures, newsletters, press releases, banners, popular articles for online magazines, audio-visual materials such as interviews, presentations with commentaries and a ROADMAP animated video to raise awareness to AMR and communicate the integrative strategies to public and policy makers. ROADMAP video will be communicated through ROADMAP TV at YouTube channel and will be promoted through social media channels (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn) of the project as well as EFFAB and FABRE-TP networks. Popular agricultural media channels and online magazines will also be used to reach to a wider audience. This page will be improved as the project progresses and communication and dissemination

materials are prepared. Media page includes 5 subpages including brochures, newsletters, press releases, ROADMAP YouTube Channel and Media Kit.

4.6.7 External Networks

ROADMAP website will be linked to other websites for related initiatives. Interactions with other relevant EU projects such as Star-Idaz, PROHEALTH, SAPHIR, Paragone, GenTORE, HealthyLivestock, One Health EJP, PanaMast, SIRCAH, DISARM and liaisons with local and European networks will be implemented to promote the transfer of the results where possible. Particular attention will be paid to liaise Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance (JPI AMR). Inputs are required from all partners.

4.6.8 Contact

Contact page includes an online contact form and the contact information of the project coordinator, project manager and ROADMAP Communication team.

ROADMAP

HOME PROJECT RESULTS NEWS & EVENTS STAKEHOLDERS CONTACT

CONTACT

Get in touch using the form below.

* Indicates required field

Name *

First Last

Email *

Comment *

Privacy *

I agree with the use of my personal data for the purpose detailed above. The privacy statement of ROADMAP applies to this use of your personal data.

CONTACT

<p><u>Project Coordinator</u></p> <p>Nicolas Fortané INRA nicolas.fortane@inra.fr</p>	<p><u>Project Manager</u></p> <p>Floriana-Alina Pordichie INRA Transfert floriana-alina.pordichie@inra.fr</p>	<p><u>Communication & Dissemination</u></p> <p>Çağrı Yüksel Kaya Kuyulu EIT AB cayla.kaya@ellab.info</p>
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5 Social media accounts

The ROADMAP project uses five different social media networks to target different stakeholder groups; YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and ResearchGate. Facebook is the most popular social network when targeting the end-users in many of the European countries. Twitter and LinkedIn are being used by companies, researchers and in particular by international, national and local policy and decision makers. It is also used by different umbrella organisations representing different parts of the society from producers to consumers. LinkedIn is targeting mainly professionals working in the sector and willing to read more about the technological and knowledge advances. It enables users to connect and share content with other professionals, including colleagues. ResearchGate is a media used mostly by researchers working in the public and private institutes including the R&I departments of companies. YouTube is used to share all kinds of audio-visual information for a broad range of stakeholders from the general public to scientists.

The social media strategy of ROADMAP aims at:

- Attracting different target groups from farmer's associations to pharmaceutical companies that are already active in animal health and AMR.
- Raising awareness to AMR and the research ROADMAP is conducting.
- Spreading news/content about the project: project content, activities, news, results etc.
- Engaging social media users and directing them to ROADMAP website.
- Enabling and facilitating interactive discussion forums at European and national scale using different social media channels.

In order to achieve the aims of ROADMAP social media strategy the actions listed below will be carried out:

- Establishment of ROADMAP stakeholder's community on Facebook
- Establishing national Facebook accounts where there are living-labs
- Identifying of key influencers in animal health in different social media channels
- Sharing of regular social media posts to inform about the progress of the project, events, news and results
- Using social media channels to actively engage with relevant stakeholders
- Preparation of targeted social media campaigns

Table 1 ROADMAP Social Media accounts

Social Media Channel	Account link
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Roadmap-H2020-2341808712742536/
Twitter	https://twitter.com/ROADMAP_H2020
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/roadmap-h2020
ResearchGate	https://www.researchgate.net/project/ROADMAP-Rethinking-Of-Antimicrobial-Decision-systems-in-the-Management-of-Animal-Production
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCGRI_SjrqahecLvxCJHmPQ/about

All partners are encouraged to follow and share above accounts. In order to engage a wider audience through social media, their content must be relevant, valuable and usable for the different target groups. Different kinds of content could (among others) be:

- Publication of research results
- Writing articles or blogs
- Publication of whitepapers

- Publication of informative videos
- Photographs
- Promoting ROADMAP or other interesting events

The social media accounts can also be used to participate in discussions on relevant social platforms.

Table 2 Relevant keywords and tags

Hashtags	Mentions
#antimicrobialuse	@ROADMAP2019
#AMU	@EFFAB
#AMR	@WUR
#animalproduction	@Inra_France
#foodsupplychain	@ACTA_asso
#innovative	@Cirad
#antimicrobialresistance	@LivUni
#AMUreduction	@cardiffuni
#livestockproduction	@JamesHuttonInst
#livestockfarming	@UniboMagazine
#animalhealth	@AarhusUni
#antimicrobials	@ILVOvlaanderen
#livinglab	@fiblorg
#datacollection	@_SLU
#costeffectiveness	@ZLTO
#dataanalysis	@FEUGA_20
#socsciAMR	

Detailed social media strategy is given under MS36 Outreach and Dissemination Plan and D7.3 Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results- ODP.

6 Conclusion

“D7.2 Website and Communication Package” will publicise the project, make project results available and facilitate their use through conventional and innovative communication and dissemination tools including digital media channels, audio-visual materials, webinars, workshops, publications, practice abstracts on the basis of EIP-AGRI to efficiently reach out to each target audience group.

A ROADMAP dedicated website that informs the project members, stakeholders and the wider public about project activities. It will serve as an important first contact point for the targeted audience. ROADMAP website is the major dissemination tool for the project. It will be regularly updated with the news, events, results etc. and it will be maintained for 2 more years after the project.

Communication material templates of the ROADMAP project will be used by all the partners of the project at local or international events, project meetings, email correspondence, etc. ROADMAP’s social media accounts will be regularly updated to reach out different target audiences. In order to engage a wider audience through social media, all partners are encouraged to follow the social media accounts of ROADMAP and share the posts with their network.

This Deliverable D7.2 has links with WP1 to WP6 and has links with Case Studies 1, 2, 3, 4.

7 Annex

Annex 1: Poster template

Annex 2: Powerpoint presentation template

Annex 3: Letter template

Annex 4: Agenda template

Annex 5: Meeting minutes template

www.roadmap-h2020.eu
@ROADMAP2019

Partner logo

Annex 1: Poster template

TITLE

Authors:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817626.

Annex 2: Powerpoint presentation template

Logo Partner

Click to add title

Click to add subtitle

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Click to add title

- Click to add text

@ROADMAP2019 2^2 www.roadmap-h2020.eu

www.roadmap-h2020.eu
@ROADMAP2019

Partner logo

Annex 3: Letter template

TITLE

Headline

Text

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817626.

Agenda

Date:
Time:
Location:
Meeting:
Expected to attend:

Time	Item	Presenter (s)

Annex 5: Meeting minutes template

Minutes of Meeting

Date:
Time:
Location:
Meeting:

Participants:
Apologies:

MINUTES

SUMMARY AND ACTION POINTS

No.	Action	Who	When
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			
6			

Minutes to be emailed to Partners by *(insert date)*.

Minutes are deemed accepted if no corrections are received within 10 days of the sent date.

Action Points will be followed up by the due dates indicated.